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Yield Response of Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) to Compost of Household Wastes under Three Irrigation Regimes

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Abstract

Study was carried out to assess the effects of compost doses on tomato yield in dry season under three irrigation regimes. The experiments were conducted in randomized complete block design with three replications where control plots, plots treated with compost at doses of 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ and plots treated with mineral fertilizers NPK 15-15-15 and Urea (46% N) constituted the treatments. Water was supplied according to three irrigation regimes of 1, 2 and 4 days interval. At the end of tomato harvest, soil samples were randomly collected from all plots for organic matter measurement. Only tomato total yield data were statistically analyzed. The results showed that compost and irrigation regimes affected tomato yield parameters. The highest values of early ripening yield (1.25 t ha⁻¹ - 1.68 t ha⁻¹), marketable yield (5.73 t ha⁻¹ - 30.34 t ha⁻¹) and total yield (7.40 t ha⁻¹ - 30.59 t ha⁻¹) were recorded on plots treated with compost and with mineral fertilizers, while the lowest values of early ripening yield (0.45 - 0.95 t ha⁻¹), marketable yield (0.84 - 1.90 t ha⁻¹) and total yield (3.58 - 4.19 t ha⁻¹) were recorded on control plots. The interaction of compost doses and irrigation regimes occurred indicating the ability of compost to improve tomato yield was closely related with level soil moisture.

Key words: Household waste compost, irrigation interval day, tomato yield.

1- Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the most important vegetables in Togo and cultivated in almost all parts of the country. Deficit water stress constitutes one of the most important factor limiting plant growth and yield in dry season when the weather is cooler and the incidence of pests and diseases is minimal. Field water management practices are the most influential factors affecting crop yield particularly in irrigated agriculture (Al-Omran *et al.*, 2005). Irrigation regime improves water use efficiency and has significant effect on the growth and yield of crops (Gudugi *et al.*, 2012).

In the country, the vegetable fields are small sizes about 0.25 – 0.50 ha and cultural methods in many cases still remain ancestral characterized by the use of rudimentary tools and low use inputs (improved seeds, mineral and organic fertilizers etc.), thus contributing to the continuous soil degradation. Farmers traditionally relied on long fallow periods to restore land fertility. However, population increasing has shortened the fallow periods and decreased the available agricultural land. Furthermore, farmers remove crop residues from the field and use them for feeding their livestock or as fuel to cook their food. Crops are grown continuously on poor soils. Indeed, soil physical properties deteriorate with change in land use. Especially with continuous cultivation, physical properties and productivity of many soils commonly decline due to decrease in organic matter content (Lal, 1986). According to Edwards and Araya (2009) compost increases soil fertility by holding and gradually releasing nutrients and building up organic matter levels in the soil, improves also the water holding capacity of the soil and makes crops better able to survive droughts. Compost is known for its efficacy on agricultural productivity increase, but little is known about its influence on tomato productivity in Southern Togo in dry season.

The objective of this work was to assess the effectiveness of household solid urban waste compost on yield of tomato grown under three irrigation regimes during the dry season in Southern Togo.

2- Materials and methods

2.1- Field experiments

Field experiments were carried out at the University of Lome in the Teaching Research and Demonstration Farm of Agronomic School during two dry seasons in 2018 and 2019. The land had been cropped previously for many years. The soil type was a ferralisol locally called “Terre de Barre” that developed from a continental deposit (Saragoni *et al.*, 1991). This soil is red, deep and suitable for almost all crops. The particle size distribution analysis revealed that soil surface layer (0 - 15 cm) of experimental site was loamy sand (Table 1). For this study, the land was manually ploughed and divided into plots with plot area of 3.84 m² (2.4 m x 1.6 m). Each plot was separated from the adjacent by 1 m interval while the replicates were separated by 1.5 m interval. Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) mongal F1, a high-yielding hybrid cultivar, was used. The tomato seedlings were raised in the nursery for three weeks before transported on plots and planted at a spacing of 0.5 m. The treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design. Each treatment was replicated three times. There were five treatments per block where T0 refers to control plots without any compost use while T20, T30 and T40 refer to plots treated with compost at 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ doses respectively and T_{MF} refers to mineral fertilizers NPK 15-15-15 and Urea (46% N) applied at 0.2 t ha⁻¹ and 0.1 t ha⁻¹ respectively. These treatments were in combination with three irrigation regimes (interval of 1, 2 and 4 days). The compost used was produced with 70% of household solid urban wastes collected from Agbalepedogan district in Lome mixed with 30% poultry manure (Alate *et al.*, 2019). It was applied at the beginning of tomato cultivation before transplanting the young tomato plants. It was spread on the soil surface after ploughing and mixed with the topsoil at about 15 cm depth. Preventive phytosanitary treatments were performed against potential pests and diseases of tomato.

2.2- Irrigation scheduling

Irrigation schedule, including 1, 2 and 4 days interval, was applied during all experimental period. At each irrigation event, an amount of water corresponding to field capacity water content in 15 cm soil depth was applied. Irrigation was applied manually using a watering can with capacity known in order to make sure that all the experimental plots received the same amount of water. Combined effect of compost doses and irrigation regimes on tomato yield parameters was evaluated.

2.3- Organic matter content determination

For the organic matter content determination, soil samples were collected randomly in surface layer (0 - 15 cm) from each plot at the end of tomato harvest. The amount of organic carbon content was measured in soil samples following the wet oxidation method of Walkley and Black (Schnitzer, 1982) while organic matter content was calculated by multiplying the organic carbon value by 1.724 based on the assumption that organic matter contains 58% organic carbon (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015).

2.4- Tomato fruit harvest

When the fruits turned yellowish red, they were harvested at a regular interval from each plot. Fruits were picked by hand at 3 days interval during three weeks. The tomato fruits were sorted into categories marketable and unmarketable (cracked fruits, unripe fruits, tiny fruits, fruits having blossom - end rot, diseased, malformed and damaged by insect pests). The first harvest in all treatments was considered as early ripening. Yield from all pickings were added up and total yield was expressed in ton per hectare. Marketable and nonmarketable fruit yields were determined at harvest from all pickings.

2.5- Statistical analysis

Only tomato total yield data were grabbed into the Excel spreadsheet and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out with the CropStat software. Means comparisons between treatments were performed with Newman & Keuls test at the threshold of 5%.

3- Results and discussion

3.1- Soil organic matter content

The particle size distribution analysis revealed that soil surface layer (0 - 15 cm) of experimental site was loamy sand (Table 1).

Table 1: Organic matter content and particle size distribution in soil surface layer (0 - 15 cm) before trials experimental

Organic matter (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Textural class
1.09	79.39	14.82	5.57	loamy sand

The plots that received compost at doses of 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ respectively showed the maximum organic matter content compared to control plots and plots that received chemical fertilizers (Table 2). The improvement in soil organic matter content is attributable to compost effect. This observation explained that compost of organic material (household waste and poultry manure) improved soil organic matter content. This observation was in line with that of previous studies (Bouajila and Sanaa, 2011; Brown and Cotton, 2011, Dadashi *et al.*, 2019). The tendency observed was the soil organic matter increased with increasing the amount of compost applied.

Table 2: Effects of compost doses and irrigation interval days on soil organic matter content

Treatments	Irrigation schedule (interval days)	2018	2019
T0	daily	0.96±0.03	1.01±0.01
	2 days	1.01±0.03	1.04±0.02
	4 days	1.02±0.03	1.03±0.03
T20	daily	2.09±0.01	2.31±0.02
	2 days	2.08±0.02	2.29±0.02
	4 days	2.09±0.03	2.32±0.03
T30	daily	2.19±0.03	2.38±0.02
	2 days	2.18±0.01	2.39±0.01
	4days	2.16±0.02	2.29±0.03
T40	daily	3.14±0.04	3.38±0.01
	2 days	3.13±0.03	3.39±0.02
	4 days	3.16±0.03	3.41±0.03
T _{MF}	daily	0.98±0.02	1.03±0.02
	2 days	1.04±0.01	1.02±0.02
	4 days	1.02±0.01	1.03±0.01

In Table 2, T0 refers to control plot without any compost use while T20, T30 and T40 refer to compost applied at 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ doses respectively. T_{MF} refers to mineral fertilizers NPK 15-15-15 and Urea (46%) applied at 0.2 t ha⁻¹ and 0.1 t ha⁻¹ respectively.

3.2- Tomato yield parameters

The tomato yield parameters (early ripening yield, marketable yield, unmarketable yield and total yield) were significantly influenced by compost doses and irrigation regimes. The highest values of early ripening yield (1.25 t ha⁻¹ - 1.68 t ha⁻¹), marketable yield (5.73 t ha⁻¹ - 30.34 t ha⁻¹) and total yield (7.40 t ha⁻¹ - 30.59 t ha⁻¹) were recorded on plots treated with compost and with mineral fertilizers, while the lowest values of

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early ripening yield (0.45 - 0.95 t ha⁻¹), marketable yield (0.84 - 1.90 t ha⁻¹) and total yield (3.58 - 4.19 t ha⁻¹) were recorded on control plots (Tables 3 & 4).

Table 3: Effects of compost doses and irrigation schedule on tomato yield parameters in 2018

Treatments	Irrigation interval days	Early ripening yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Marketable yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Unmarketable yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Total yield (t ha ⁻¹)
T0	daily	0.79±0.03	1.50±0.04	2.55±0.03	4.05±0.02g
	2 days	0.95±0.03	1.90±0.03	2.29±0.02	4.19±0.02g
	4 days	0.86±0.02	1.02±0.03	2.90±0.03	3.92±0.03g
T20	daily	1.39±0.01	5.73±0.03	1.72±0.02	7.45±0.02f
	2 days	1.45±0.03	13.26±0.01	0.94±0.04	14.20±0.04d
	4 days	1.25±0.03	5.87±0.03	1.55±0.03	7.42±0.03f
T30	daily	1.40±0.03	8.73±0.03	1.64±0.01	10.37±0.04e
	2 days	1.50±0.03	19.37±0.03	0.75±0.02	20.12±0.04b
	4 days	1.30±0.03	5.90±0.03	1.50±0.03	7.40±0.03f
T40	daily	1.45±0.02	8.88±0.02	1.51±0.02	10.39±0.03e
	2 days	1.63±0.03	24.28±0.02	0.56±0.03	24.84±0.02a
	4 days	1.33±0.01	6.04±0.03	1.44±0.03	7.48±0.03f
T _{MF}	daily	1.25±0.02	8.81±0.02	1.54±0.02	10.35±0.03e
	2 days	1.26±0.03	17.63±0.02	0.91±0.03	18.54±0.02c
	4 days	1.27±0.01	5.88±0.03	1.53±0.03	7.41±0.03f

In Table 3, T0 refers to control plot without any compost use while T20, T30 and T40 refer to compost applied at 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ doses respectively. T_{MF} refers to mineral fertilizers NPK 15-15-15 and Urea (46%) applied at 0.2 t ha⁻¹ and 0.1 t ha⁻¹ respectively. In total yield column, treatment mean values followed by same letter are not significantly different at the threshold of 5%.

However, the highest values of unmarketable yield (2.29 t ha⁻¹ - 2.90 t ha⁻¹) were recorded on control plots, while the lowest values of this parameter (0.25 t ha⁻¹ - 1.80 t ha⁻¹) were found on the plots treated with compost and chemical fertilizers (Tables 3 & 4).

The lowest values (0.25 t ha⁻¹ - 0.96 t ha⁻¹) of cracked fruits and blossom-end rot fruits (unmarketable fruits) observed on the plants irrigated at two days interval and the highest values (1.25 t ha⁻¹ - 1.80 t ha⁻¹) of this parameter recorded on plots under irrigation at four days interval and on plots under daily irrigation (Tables 3 & 4) explained interactive effect between the irrigation regimes and doses of compost and chemical fertilizers.

The effect of irrigation interval on fruit yield in both 2018 and 2019 dry seasons was recorded such that two days irrigation interval gave higher total yields (14.20 t ha⁻¹ - 30.59 t ha⁻¹) while the lowest total yields (7.40 t ha⁻¹ - 11.70 t ha⁻¹) were recorded at daily irrigation and at four days interval irrigation. This is in line with the findings of Gudugi *et al.* (2012) that higher number of tomato fruits had been reported to be related with irrigation intervals.

The interaction of compost doses and irrigation regimes occurred indicating the ability of compost to improve tomato yield was closely related with level soil moisture. This tendency might be attributed to the fact that adequate watering conditions led to the development of an abundant ovules per floret consequently higher yield fruit.

Table 4: Effects of compost doses and irrigation schedule on tomato yield parameters in 2019

Treatments	Irrigation interval days	Early ripening yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Marketable yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Unmarketable yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Total yield (t ha ⁻¹)
T0	daily	0.50±0.01	0.84±0.01	2.78±0.01	3.62±0.01g
	2 days	0.67±0.02	1.30±0.02	2.35±0.01	3.65±0.01g
	4 days	0.45±0.01	0.88±0.02	2.70±0.02	3.58±0.02g
	daily	1.40±0.01	7.00±0.02	1.49±0.02	8.49±0.01f

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T20	2 days	1.46±0.02	17.34±0.02	0.45±0.03	17.79±0.02c
	4 days	1.28±0.02	6.78±0.01	1.75±0.02	8.53±0.01f
T30	daily	1.41±0.02	10.18±0.01	1.39±0.02	11.57±0.01d
	2 days	1.55±0.01	25.23±0.02	0.33±0.01	25.56±0.03b
	4 days	1.31±0.03	8.65±0.03	1.60±0.02	10.25±0.02e
T40	daily	1.44±0.03	10.28±0.03	1.35±0.01	11.63±0.01d
	2 days	1.68±0.02	30.34±0.01	0.25±0.01	30.59±0.03a
	4 days	1.35±0.02	9.01±0.01	1.25±0.02	10.26±0.02e
T _{MF}	daily	1.29±0.02	9.90±0.02	1.80±0.02	11.70±0.03d
	2 days	1.33±0.03	24.45±0.02	0.96±0.03	25.41±0.02b
	4 days	1.25±0.01	8.49±0.03	1.75±0.03	10.24±0.03e

In Table 4, T0 refers to control plot without any compost use while T20, T30 and T40 refer to compost applied at 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ doses respectively. T_{MF} refers to mineral fertilizers NPK 15-15-15 and Urea (46%) applied at 0.2 t ha⁻¹ and 0.1 t ha⁻¹ respectively. In total yield column, treatment mean values followed by same letter are not significantly different at the threshold of 5%.

The higher yield fruits (early ripening yield, marketable yield and total yield) obtained at two days irrigation interval in this study might be due to optimal conditions of soil moisture during the study period. As soil moisture conserving was suitable at two days irrigation interval, the improvement of marketable yield of the tomato resulted mainly from the increase in average fruits weight. These findings are supported by Abdel-Razzak *et al.* (2016). They found that the marketable yield enhancement of the tomato cultivars was correlated to irrigation regime.

Decreasing yield recorded on plots irrigated every day may be explained by the excess irrigation which would lead to water draining past the root zone, leaching nutrients and reducing water and nutrient use efficiency. This explains that water use efficiency rises with increase of water supply up to a certain point. According to Prihar *et al.* (1985), water supply has been observed to increase fertilizer use efficiency by increasing the availability of applied nutrients. Too much water in the root zone would reduce also the amount of oxygen available and leading to plant stress (Morard *et al.*, 2000; Boru *et al.*, 2003; Iwasaki, 2008; Rajanna *et al.*, 2018). In conditions of too frequent irrigation, the roots were without air after each irrigation until the free water has drained from the soil profile. During this time, plant growth and development nearly would stop.

In other hand, the reduction in yield of plants irrigated at four days interval indicates that these plants were subjected to water deficit stress and yield decreasing may be explained by effect of water deficit stress (Bouazzama *et al.*, 2012; Dhakar *et al.*, 2018). Decreasing yield recorded from these plants may be explained by the high percent abortion observed on these severe stressed plants due to the fact that as the water stress increases, the number of ovules per floret decreases. Lower soil moisture may lead to the flower abortion and fewer fruits. Adams *et al.* (2001) reported that poor fruits set was observed at high temperatures. In this study, temperature in the air was higher during the experiment because conducted in dry season. Birhanu and Tilahun (2010) reported a decreased number and sizes of tomato fruits from plants subjected to moisture stress. The same observation of water stress on tomato yield parameters was also reported by Zotarelli *et al.* (2009).

4- Conclusion

Based on preliminary results recorded, the compost doses 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ improved proportionally tomato yield under irrigation regimes studied. It can be concluded that the application of household solid urban waste compost at the minimum dose of 20 t ha⁻¹ on red soil "Terre de Barre" in southern Togo under regime of two days irrigation interval in dry season could improve significantly the tomato yield.

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6- References

- i. Abdel-Razzak, H., Wahb-Allah, M., Ibrahim, A., Alenazi, M. and Alsadon, A. (2016). Response of Cherry Tomato to Irrigation Levels and Fruit Pruning under Greenhouse Conditions. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 18: 1091-1103.
- ii. Adams, S.R., Cockshull, K.E. and Cave, C.R.J. (2001). Effect of temperature on the growth and development of tomato fruits. *Annals of Botany*, 88(5):869–877.
- iii. Alate, K.K.A., Mawussi, G., Ayisah, K.D. and Sanda, K. (2019). Agronomic potential value of household urban solid wastes by composting and composts quality assessment. *International Journal of Agricultural Research, Innovation and Technology*, 9(2): 1-8.
- iv. Al-Omran, A.M., Sheta, A.S., Falatah, A.M. and Al-Harbi, A.R. (2005). Effect of Drip Irrigation on Squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) Yield and Water-use Efficiency in Sandy Calcareous Soils Amended with Clay Deposits. *Agricultural Water Management*, 73: 43-55.
- v. Birhanu, K. and Tilahun, K. (2010). Fruit yield and quality of dripped-irrigated tomato under deficit irrigation. *African journal of food agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 10(2): 2139-2151.
- vi. Boru, G., Vantoai, T., Alves, J., Hua D. and Knee, M. (2003). Responses of soybean to oxygen deficiency and elevated root-zone carbon dioxide concentration. *Annals of Botany*, 91: 447-453.
- vii. Bouajila, K. and Sanaa, M. (2011). Effects of organic amendments on soil physico-chemical and biological properties. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 2, 485 – 490.
- viii. Bouazzama, B., Xanthoulis, D., Bouaziz, A., Ruelle, P. and Mailhol J.-C. (2012). Effect of water stress on growth, water consumption and yield of silage maize under flood irrigation in a semi-arid climate of Tadla (Morocco). *Biotechnology, Agronomy, Society and Environment*, 16(4): 468-477.
- ix. Brown, S. and Cotton, M. (2011). Changes in Soil Properties and Carbon Content Following Compost Application: Results of On-farm Sampling. *Compost Science and Utilization*, 19(1), 88-97.
- x. Dadashi, S., Ghajar Sepanlou, M. and Mirnia, S.Kh. (2019). Influence organic compost compounds on soil chemical and physical properties. *International Journal of Human Capital in Urban Management*, 4(1) 15-22.
- xi. Dhakar, R., Chandran, M.A.S., Nagar, S., Kumari, V.V., Subbarao, A.V.M., Bal, S.K. and P. Kumar P.V. (2018). Field crop response to water deficit stress: Assessment through crop models. *Advances in Crop Environment Interaction*, 11: 287-315.
- xii. Edwards, S. and Araya, H. (2009). The Tigray Project: organic agriculture with smallholder farmers in a mountainous environment. *Ecology & Farming*, 28-30.
- xiii. Gudugi, I.A.S, Odojin, A.J, Adeboye, M.K.A and Oladiran, J.A. (2012). Agronomic characteristics of tomato as influenced by irrigation and mulching. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 3(5): 2539-2543.
- xiv. Ibrahim, M.M., Mahmoud, E.K. and Ibrahim, D.A. (2015). Effects of vermicompost and water treatment residuals on soil physical properties and wheat yield. *International Agrophysics*, 29, 157-164.
- xv. Iwasaki, Y. (2008). Root zone aeration improves growth and yields of coir-cultured straw berry (*Fragaria ananassa* Duch.) during summer. *Acta Horticulturae*, 779: 251-254.
- xvi. Lal, R. (1986). Conversion of tropical rainforest: Agronomic potential and ecological consequences. *Advances in Agronomy*, 39: 173-263.
- xvii. Morard, P., Lacoste, L. and Silvestre J. (2000). Effect of oxygen deficiency on uptake of water and mineral nutrients by tomato plants in soilless culture. *Journal of Plant Nutrition* 23(8):1063-1078.

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- xviii. Prihar, S.S., Gajri, P.R. and Arora, V.K. (1985). Nitrogen fertilization of wheat under limited water supplies. *Fertilizer Research*, 8:1-8.
- xix. Rajanna, G.A., Dass, A. and Paramesha, V. (2018). Excess Water Stress: Effects on Crop and Soil, and Mitigation Strategies. *Popular Kheti*, 6(3): 48-53.
- xx. Saragoni, H., Olivier, R. and Poss, R. (1991). Dynamique et lixiviation des éléments minéraux. *Agronomie Tropicale*. 45(4): 259-273.
- xxi. Schnitzer, M. (1982). Total carbon, organic matter, and carbon. In: *Methods of Soil Analysis Part II*. Page, A.L. (Ed.). *Chemical and Microbiological Properties*. American Society of Agronomy, Madison. Part 2, *Agronomy Monograph*, 9, 2nd ed., WI. 539 – 577.
- xxii. Zotarelli, L., Scholberg, J.M., Dukes, M. D., Munoz Carpena, R. and Icerman, J. (2009). Tomato yield, biomass accumulation, root distribution and irrigation water use efficiency on a sandy soil, as affected by nitrogen rate and irrigation scheduling. *Agricultural water management*, 9(6), 23-34.